

Deep Learning in a Simulated Environment Using The MLAgents Library

Emanuel Martinez

*#Engineering and Computer Science, Syracuse University
900 South Crouse Ave*

*Syracuse NY, United States of America
emarti46@syr.edu*

Abstract— This paper explores various methods for creating and iteratively improving neural networks trained in simulated environments. The focus is on two primary approaches: (1) reinforcement learning, where the model learns autonomously, and (2) imitation learning, where the model learns from recorded input samples provided by the programmer. The study utilizes the MLAgents library to implement these learning paradigms within a simulated environment. The paper discusses the algorithms underlying these learning methods, particularly the policy gradient method and the Generative Adversarial Imitation Learning (GAIL) algorithm policy schema.

Keywords— deep learning, Unity game engine, game development, 3D simulation, machine learning algorithms, reinforcement learning, imitation learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The simulation of training environments is fundamental to testing and advancing ideas in reinforcement learning research (Juliani et al., 2020). To facilitate progress in the field of AI, there is a growing need for more accessible and versatile testing environments. This paper presents two methods for teaching and creating neural networks within such simulated environments.

The first method involves an AI agent with extrinsic knowledge of simulated objects learning to reach a specified target. The complexity of tasks then increases, culminating in a more involved problem where the agent must activate a button to dispense food and subsequently "eat" the reward. The agent receives positive reinforcement for achieving each part of the task, while continuous negative rewards are applied to encourage speed.

This paper delves into the algorithms that enable this form of reinforcement learning, specifically examining the policy gradient method and the Generative Adversarial Imitation Learning (GAIL)

algorithm policy schema. By exploring these approaches, we aim to provide insights into the development of more effective and efficient AI learning models within simulated environments.

II. ENVIRONMENT

Reinforcement learning occupies a unique position in machine learning, combining elements of both supervised and unsupervised learning. The algorithms employed in reinforcement learning iterate over policies to improve upon previous behaviors exhibited in a simulated environment.

Characteristics of an Ideal Reinforcement Learning Environment

To understand why the Unity game engine is an appropriate choice for reinforcement learning, it's crucial to examine the qualifying properties of an ideal learning environment:

- A. **Sensory Complexity:** The environment must support various forms of sensory input, primarily visual, but potentially including auditory and barometric responses for more complex models. This allows the agent to process and interpret objects, images, and text within its virtual world.
- B. **Physical Complexity:** The environment should accurately simulate real-world physics, including properties such as mass, weight, volume, and velocity. This enables the agent to make optimal decisions in physics-based problem sets,

such as those related to balance, fluid dynamics, and aerodynamics.

- C. **Task Logic Complexity:** The environment must support the implementation of complex task logic, allowing the agent to evaluate task difficulty and weigh the probability of success accurately.
- D. **Social Complexity:** For multi-agent scenarios, the environment should facilitate inter-agent communication and coordination, defining how agents interact with external stimuli and each other.

Simulation Properties

Beyond these fundamental properties, the quality of the reinforcement learning environment also depends on its simulation capabilities:

1. **Speed and Efficiency:** As modern machine learning algorithms often require billions of samples to converge on optimal solutions (Espeholt et al., 2018; Puigdomènech Badia et al., 2020), the speed and efficiency of the simulation significantly impact the outcome.
2. **Control Flexibility:** The environment should offer variable control over task complexity, allowing researchers to fine-tune the learning process.

While various existing environments offer many of these properties, the Unity game engine stands out for its comprehensive coverage of all the necessary features. Its higher-level abstraction and interfaces make it particularly well-suited for conducting quality AI research, surpassing even comparable game engines like Unreal in this regard.

III. POLICY GRADIENT METHODS

One of the most significant challenges in reinforcement learning stems from the dynamic nature of training within simulated environments. Unlike the static datasets typical in supervised learning models, reinforcement learning requires

agents to optimize their policies based on continually changing conditions. This dynamism can lead to high sensitivity in hyperparameter tuning, particularly in aspects such as initialization.

Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

To address these challenges, researchers and developers at OpenAI have introduced the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. The primary objectives of PPO are to:

1. Simplify hyperparameter tuning
2. Enhance sampling efficiency
3. Facilitate easier coding for training platforms

PPO implements practical occupancy measuring algorithms, replacing the need for extensive data storage with continuous online learning. In this approach, the agent iterates on its own policies, with each experience triggering a gradient update. Previous experiences are discarded to make way for improvements, ensuring the agent's policy remains current and adaptive.

Efficiency Comparison

While policy gradient methods offer significant advantages, they can be less sample-efficient compared to other approaches. Figure 1 illustrates the performance difference between Deep Q-Network (DQN), REINFORCE, and Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C) algorithms over 20,000 episodes in the VizDoom Defend the Center environment, a simulator based on the Doom game engine.

[Figure 1: Inefficient use of samples by policy gradient methods compared to other policy methods]

Fig. 1 Inefficient use of samples by policy gradient methods compared to other policy methods

Policy Optimization

The policy gradient loss is defined as the expectation over the log of the policy actions multiplied by an estimate of the advantage function:

$$LPG(\theta) = \mathbb{E}[\log \pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t)A_t]$$

Where:

- π_{θ} represents a neural network that takes observed states from the environment as input and suggests actions as output, thus constituting the policy
- A_t is the advantage function, estimating the relative value of the selected action in the current state

To compute the advantage function, we need:

1. The discounted rewards sum
2. A baseline estimate

The discounted rewards can be summarized as the weighted sum of all rewards received by the agent during each time step in a particular episode:

$$R_t = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k * r(t+k)$$

The discount factor γ , typically between 0.9 and 0.99, prioritizes immediate rewards over long-term rewards. This concept is analogous to financial interest, where an earlier return on investment is generally preferred.

PPO Algorithm Design

[Figure 2: PPO algorithm design]

Algorithm 1 PPO, Actor-Critic Style

```

for iteration=1, 2, ... do
  for actor=1, 2, ..., N do
    Run policy  $\pi_{\theta_{old}}$  in environment for  $T$  timesteps
    Compute advantage estimates  $\hat{A}_1, \dots, \hat{A}_T$ 
  end for
  Optimize surrogate  $L$  wrt  $\theta$ , with  $K$  epochs and minibatch size  $M \leq NT$ 
   $\theta_{old} \leftarrow \theta$ 
end for

```

Fig. 2 PPO algorithm design

The PPO algorithm computes the discounted return ahead of time, eliminating guesswork from decision-making. The baseline estimate, also known as the value function, attempts to predict the discounted sum of rewards in the current episode, estimating the value of the final return from the current state.

Generative Adversarial Imitation Learning (GAIL)

Characterizing the approximate cost of a reinforcement learning model often requires transforming optimization problems across a range of policies into convex problems. For any given policy in a set, its occupancy measure can be quantified as the range of all qualified state-action pairs defined by the resultant policy, given a qualified action pair, over the probability of that state's recurrence under the original policy.

The occupancy of all state-action pairs available to the agent represents the distribution of expert policies, their state-action pairs, and associated costs and cost functions. These dynamic models are derived from the set of policies where an action's state is highly likely under certain policies, provided it is a qualified state. Ultimately, all policies correspond to the dynamic model, and the dynamic model corresponds to its policies.

Entropy-Regularized Apprenticeship Learning

In entropy-regularized apprenticeship learning, we define two classes of cost functions:

1. Linear cost functions:
 $\mathcal{C}_{linear} = \{\sum_i w_i * f_i : ||w||_2 \leq 1\}$
2. Convex cost functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_{convex} &= \{\sum_i w_i * f_i : \sum_i w_i \\ &= 1, w_i \geq 0 \forall i\} \end{aligned}$$

If $\mathcal{C}$ does not include a cost function that adequately explains expert behavior, attempting to recover a policy from such an encoding will not succeed.

Apprenticeship learning with restrictive cost classes $\mathcal{C}$ can scale to large state and action spaces through policy function approximation. This involves:

1. Defining a policy gradient formula
2. Establishing an apprenticeship objective
3. Parameterizing the policy π_θ
4. Fitting cost functions
5. Evaluating analytical expressions
6. Estimating gradients

A policy gradient for a reinforcement learning objective has a conjugate cost. Ho et al. proposed an algorithm that alternates between two steps:

1. Fit a cost function to the sample of the current policy's trajectory in the simulation.
2. Use the conjugate cost to form a gradient estimate and produce an inductive parameterized policy.

This approach to policy optimization is called Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO). The natural gradient step is crucial to the algorithm and is constrained to ensure that π_{i+1} does not deviate too far from π_i , as measured by a constant distance divergence factor between the two policies, averaged over the states in the sampled trajectories.

To characterize the approximate cost of the reinforcement learning model tentatively requires transforming optimization problems of some range of policies into convex problems. For some policy in a set its occupancy measure can be quantified as the range of all qualified state action pairs that are defined by the resultant policy given a qualified action pair over the probability of that state's recurrence provided the original policy. The occupancy of all state-action pairs available to the agent is the distribution of all expert policies, their state-action pairs, as well as their costs and cost functions. These dynamic models are derived from the set of policies from which an action's state is highly likely with certain policies in place; provided it is a qualified state. Ultimately all policies correspond to the dynamic model, and the dynamic model to its policies.

A. Entropy Regularized Apprenticeship Learning

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$$\mathcal{C}_{linear} = \{\sum_i w_i f_i : ||w||_2 \leq 1\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}_{convex} = \{\sum_i w_i f_i : \sum_i w_i = 1, w_i \geq 0 \forall i\}$$

If $\mathcal{C}$ does not include a cost function that explains expert behavior well, then attempting to recover a policy from such an encoding will not succeed.

Apprenticeship learning with restrictive cost classes $\mathcal{C}$ can scale to large state and action spaces with policy function approximation. Policy gradient formula. Apprenticeship objective. parameterized policy π_θ . Cost fitting. Evaluate analytical expressions. Gradient estimate. A policy gradient for a reinforcement learning objective has a conjugate cost. There exists an algorithm proposed by Ho et al. that alternates between two steps:

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paramaterized policy

Inducing a policy optimization in this way is called trust region policy optimization TRPO. The natural gradient step is a crucial part of the algorithm. It is constrained to ensure that $\pi_{\theta_{i+1}}$ does not stray too far from π_{θ_i} as measured by a constant distance divergence factor between the two policies averaged over the states in the sampled trajectories.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Reinforcement Learning Model

The implementation in this study follows the typical reinforcement learning model, which iterates through a cycle of:

1. Observation
2. Decision
3. Action
4. Reward

This cycle then repeats, returning to the observation phase.

Virtual Environment Setup

A virtual environment is essential for facilitating communication between the training environment and the agent's actual training data. Within the Unity engine, the primary script attached to the agent is the Behavior Parameters script.

Action Spaces

For this implementation, the agent primarily interacts with two types of action spaces:

1. **Continuous Actions:** Represented by arrays of real numbers.
2. **Discrete Branches:** Represented by arrays of integers.

Continuous Actions

Continuous actions require only specifying the number of desired actions the agent will perform.

These are typically used for actions that can take on a range of values, such as movement in a continuous space.

Discrete Branches

Discrete actions necessitate the use of branches to isolate specific actions. These are typically used for actions that have a finite set of possible values, such as choosing between a set of distinct options.

Testing Action Outputs

To determine the actual output of each action array, we can access the data structure within the Actuators library. This process involves:

1. Accessing the relevant class
2. Retrieving the contents of the action array
3. Sending the contents to an output log for visualization

Figure 3 illustrates the output of a discrete branch with 5 specified actions:

[Figure 3: Output contents of a discrete branch with 5 specified actions]

This approach allows for verification of the action space and ensures that the agent is correctly interpreting and executing actions within the simulated environment.

Fig. 3 Output contents of a discrete branch with 5 specified actions

Observation Space Design

With a working knowledge of the action space, the next step is to design the observation space - the data the AI needs to solve the given problem set. In our example, the agent requires knowledge of its own position and the target's position.

Vector Representation

Observations are collected and stored as vectors. The physics information stored by the game engine can be leveraged to make this information accessible to the sensor class. In a 3D engine, where agent information follows a three-dimensional paradigm, the space required for storing vectors includes:

- Agent's position: (x, y, z)
- Target object's position: (x, y, z)

Thus, a total of 6 vectors are stored for reuse.

Training Configuration

Based on this observation space, we can define the training configuration as requiring 6 vectors (3 for agent position, 3 for target position) with two continuous actions to represent movement in the x and z axes.

Reward System

The reward system can be implemented in two primary ways:

1. **Incremental Rewarding:** Providing small rewards for progress towards the goal.
2. **Completion Rewarding:** Specifying a reward amount to be given upon successful completion of the task.

At the point of reward distribution, the end of the episode can also be defined. The desired outcome is for the agent's position to be reset when a new episode begins.

It's crucial to implement a penalty system for task failure to produce functional learning. This creates a balanced reward structure that encourages desired behaviors while discouraging undesired ones.

Heuristic Controls for Imitation Learning

To streamline testing and prepare for imitation learning, heuristic controls are implemented. This feature allows direct input from an input device to the action buffer array, facilitating human demonstration of desired behaviors.

Training Execution

With all important functions in place, training can begin by:

1. Executing the proper command
2. Assigning a descriptive name to the test
3. Running the test

Accelerating Training

To expedite the process, it's possible to replicate the testing environment multiple times before executing the agent training protocol. This parallel training approach can significantly reduce overall training time.

Neural Network Output and Iteration

Upon completion or cessation of training, an output file is generated. This file serves as the neural network, bearing the same name used in the Behavior Parameters script. This neural network becomes the model from which policy decisions are derived by passing it into the behavior parameters class.

The agent can use these decision metrics to further improve its decision-making capabilities as needed. From this point, it's possible to extend the hyperparameters by:

1. Specifying to the command line the inclusion of a custom markup language file containing all custom hyperparameters.
2. Indicating the location of this file.

Furthermore, at this stage, it becomes possible to specify:

- The policy gradient

- The learning algorithm(s) to be used

This configuration allows the neural network to iterate on itself even more, potentially leading to improved performance over time.

VI. Data Extraction

TensorBoard Integration

The ML-Agents Toolkit is designed to seamlessly integrate with TensorFlow, leveraging an extended library called TensorBoard. This powerful tool enables real-time visualization and analysis of test data as experiments are being conducted.

Execution and Access

To utilize TensorBoard for data extraction and visualization:

1. Execution:

- Open a command line interface within a virtual environment.
- Execute the appropriate command to launch TensorBoard.
- Specify the directory of the output logs (by default, this directory is named "results").

2. Access:

- Once TensorBoard is running, open a web browser.
- Navigate to <http://localhost:6006> to access the TensorBoard interface.

This setup allows for immediate and interactive exploration of training metrics and performance data.

Fig. 4 TensorBoard visualization of training results

Interpreting TensorBoard Results

Figure 4 illustrates the expected results from our training sessions:

Cumulative Reward

The graph demonstrates a consistent increase in cumulative reward over time. This upward trend indicates that the agent is successfully learning and improving its performance on the given task.

Episode Length

The Episode Length graph shows a decreasing trend as the number of episodes increases. This inverse relationship suggests that the agent is completing the goal more efficiently over time, requiring fewer steps to achieve the desired outcome.

Failure Indicators

It's important to note that if the training results in significant failures, the cumulative reward graph would exhibit a flattening line, indicating a lack of improvement or learning.

VII. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the significant potential of leveraging video game engines for AI research and development, particularly in the domain of reinforcement learning. Several key conclusions can be drawn:

1. **Accessibility of Complex Environments:** Video game engines provide readily accessible and highly configurable environments that meet the demanding requirements of AI research. These engines offer a cost-effective means to simulate complex, real-world scenarios without the need for expensive physical resources.
2. **Accelerated Real-World Applications:** The ease of implementation and the richness of simulated environments can potentially accelerate the development of real-world machine learning applications. This approach bridges the gap between theoretical models and practical implementations.
3. **Interdisciplinary Opportunities:** Small teams with diverse skill sets, such as those typically involved in video game development, can make significant contributions to AI research. Their expertise in creating immersive, interactive environments is directly applicable to designing effective training scenarios for AI agents.
4. **Need for Creative Solutions:** As the field of AI continues to advance, there is an increasing demand for innovative approaches to designing high-quality training environments. The flexibility and power of game engines position them as ideal platforms for meeting this need.

5. **Seamless Tool Integration:** Those who can effectively utilize the tools available in these general platform environments are well-positioned to drive advancements in AI research and development. The ability to seamlessly integrate various components of the AI pipeline - from environment design to data visualization - is crucial for efficient and effective experimentation.

In conclusion, the integration of game engine technology with machine learning frameworks presents a promising avenue for advancing AI research. It offers a unique combination of accessibility, flexibility, and power that can significantly contribute to the development of more sophisticated and capable AI systems. As we move forward, the continued exploration and refinement of these approaches will likely play a crucial role in shaping the future of artificial intelligence and its real-world applications.

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